

LONG TERM BEHAVIOR OF MACROECONOMIC INDICATORS IN UZBEKISTAN

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In most countries researches are done to know relations of all economic sectors of country and this survey is more important to central Asian countries, they are compared with econometric model of Uzbekistan.

The gross domestic product (GDP) measures of national income and output for a given country's economy. The gross domestic product (GDP) is equal to the total expenditures for all final goods and services produced within the country in a stipulated period of time.

This survey done using statistics gathered during past 22 years (time span is from 2000 to 2021). To determine globally, I used 3 macroeconomic indicators of Uzbekistan made comparisons where relevant: GDP, FDI and unemployment.

Economic growth of a nation is the increase in a nation's real output that occurs over time. In general, growth and unemployment are closely related as unemployment affects the growth rate through the scale of operation of an economy. Besides that, FDI inflow is taken into account altogether to identify the relationship towards the unemployment rate and its contribution on GDP. All factors are related each other in terms of showing growth.

Uzbekistan GDP for 2021 was 65.503 billion USD and ranked 75th place in among all countries. There were rise than previous 2 years of pandemic (in 2021 59.928 billion USD and in 2019 59.907 billion USD) , while neighborhoods' GDP differ from each other: Kazakhstan 194.024 billion USD, Kyrgyz 8.15 billion USD, Turkmenistan 53.087 billion USD, Tajikistan 8.104 billion USD and Afghanistan 21.222 billion USD.

GDP is the most highlighted indicator to rank country's economic capability globally. In the case of Uzbekistan I observed 22 observations, there are: GDP is considered as dependent variable, econometric models below shows the impact of all other factor to dependent variable, independent variables are FDI entered during given time span, unemployment rate.

Figure 1 Graph illustrating correlation of GDP and impact (FDI and Unemployment)

This graph illustrates GDP alteration within years. Thus, below I made further scrutinizes, because the graph only cannot represent clear condition of GDP and other influential factors.

I used OLS method. [Ordinary Least Squares \(OLS\)](#) is the most common estimation method for linear models—and that's true for a good reason. As long as your model satisfies the OLS assumptions for linear [regression](#), you can rest easy knowing that you're getting the best possible [estimates](#). [Regression](#) is a powerful analysis that can analyze multiple variables simultaneously to answer complex research questions. There are seven classical OLS assumptions for linear regression. The first six are mandatory to produce the best estimates. I exploited them step by step.

To begin with, I calculated correlation between macro indicators.

	Unempl~t	gdp	fdi
Unemployment	1.0000		
gdp	-0.3073	1.0000	
fdi	0.2302	0.5290	1.0000

Figure 2 Correlation matrix of GDP, FDI, unemployment of Uzbekistan

According to the table from stata program, GDP and unemployment are negatively correlated. If this coefficient is more than 0.7, they would correlate strong positive. To clarify multi collinearity I checked correlation of independent variables to VIF test. The results are acceptable, that is if the result of vif test id lower than 10, we can accept that variables are not multi collinear. In our case it is lower than 2, so we can use this model.

FDI and GDP relation is good, they highlight 0.5290, and it means they are positively correlated. It is the initial stage in composing model. Correlation matrix shows that all variables correlated normal with dependent variable.

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. reg gdp Unemployment fdi
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Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	22
Model	4694.46498	2	2347.23249	F(2, 19)	=	8.57
Residual	5204.36149	19	273.913763	Prob > F	=	0.0022
				R-squared	=	0.4742
				Adj R-squared	=	0.4189
Total	9898.82647	21	471.372689	Root MSE	=	16.55

gdp	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Unemployment	-3.136797	1.183344	-2.65	0.016	-5.613564 - .6600305
fdi	11.12048	3.001677	3.70	0.002	4.837896 17.40306
_cons	51.9165	9.481836	5.48	0.000	32.07079 71.76222

Figure 3 Table of regression for first linear model

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. reg lngdp fdi Unemployment
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Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	22
Model	6.14085809	2	3.07042905	F(2, 19)	=	12.80
Residual	4.55627929	19	.239804173	Prob > F	=	0.0003
Total	10.6971374	21	.509387494	R-squared	=	0.5741
				Adj R-squared	=	0.5292
				Root MSE	=	.4897

lngdp	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
fdi	.3776459	.0888148	4.25	0.000	.1917543 .5635374
Unemployment	-.1277598	.0350132	-3.65	0.002	-.2010433 -.0544762
_cons	4.058559	.2805523	14.47	0.000	3.471357 4.645762

Figure 4 Table of regression for second log-linear model

Figure 3 and 4 are the tables of the regression, it provides with standard error of our model, and confidence intervals to assure the correctness of situation with 95% confidence.

These two models show relevant coefficients that help us to identify correctness of the model. Coefficients are r-square, r-adjuster and p-value, and others. R stands for regression and r-square means how much strong relation of our variables. R-adjuster means how much relation of variables are reliable. If you look through the models one by one, you can notice the differences while comparing the numbers.

I chose the second one, log-linear model, because r-adjuster and r-square both are higher than linear model (first model).

Our first model shows that unemployment and the other two indicators shows irrelevance, because r-adjuster is 0.53 that our model is true for 53%. It is the result of different trends occurred among them: unemployment decreased while other two increased over the 22years.

R-square is equal to 0.57. If r is higher than zero it is positive relation, if it is lower than it is negative relation. In the second model this number is higher than first one.

P-value of the second model is also acceptable, as it is lower than $0.05 > 0.0003$. The mistake occurrence possibility in this model is 0.0003.

It and other results below prove that the economy of Uzbekistan has become stronger than Soviet Union years.

The model is the good example of that:

$$\text{Ln (Gross Domestic Product)} = -0.13 \text{ Unemployment} + 0.38 \text{ FDI} + 4.06$$

According to it FDI more effective than unemployment, because the more invest means the more job vacancies. In this case, if unemployment and FDI rise by 1 percentage point, it will effect to economic growth with 13% and 38% change respectively on dependent variable (if other factors are not neglected), economic growth .

To make it more clearly, I use T-test using table below.

According to table $b_1 = -0.13$ and standard error (se) of first parameter is 0.35; for second parameter of the model these equal to 0.378 and 0.89 respectively for the last parameter $b_3 = 4.1$ while $se(b_3) = 0.3$

$$\text{Hypothesis 0: } \beta = 0 \quad t(\text{value}) = b/se(b)$$

$$\text{Hypothesis 1: } \beta \neq 0 \quad t(\text{value}) > t(\text{ratio})$$

$$t(\text{ratio}) = \text{const} = 1.325$$

From calculations t value for three parameters will be significant.

The skew test or histogram helps to identify whether variables are normally distributed according to years or not.

Figure 5 Histogram of GDP distribution by years

From the histogram it is obvious that GDP, FDI and Unemployment are not normally distributed. GDP increased at the end of period.

Suppose that if coming year in Uzbekistan foreign direct investment increases by 5 billion USD and as a result further job vacancies will definitely appear and this leads to a decrease in unemployment to 7.6 percentage points. Concluding calculation above, we can surely project the GDP with 95% confidence if two variables change according to the statement above. For its work out, we need confidence interval.

$$GDP_0 - se(f) \cdot t(c) \leq GDP \leq GDP_0 + se(f) \cdot t(c)$$

Se(f) from figure 4 $se(f)=12.8$

GDP₀ is calculated according to the given statement.

$\ln(GDP) = -0.13 \cdot 7.6 + 0.38 \cdot 5 + 4.06 = 144.32$ billion USD (approximately)

$T(c) = \text{const} = 2.093$

$117.5 \text{ billion USD} < GDP < 171.11 \text{ billion USD}$ We estimated that if variables change according to the statement given GDP will be in this interval with 95% possibility.

Despite dramatic growth of GDP, FDI during last years, in 2020 these two fell significantly, this fall happened by the impact of COVID. Pandemic not only affected the economy of Uzbekistan, economy of the world is also ruined too. As António Guterres, Secretary-General of the United Nations said: "Global flows of foreign direct investment (FDI) will be under severe pressure this year as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. These vital resources are expected to fall sharply from 2019 levels of \$1.5 trillion, dropping well below the trough reached during the global financial crisis and undoing the already lackluster growth in international investment over the past decade. Flows to developing countries will be hit especially hard, as export-oriented and commodity-linked investments are among the most seriously affected. The consequences could last well beyond the immediate impact on investment flows. Indeed, the crisis could be a catalyst for a process of structural

transformation of international production this decade, and an opportunity for increased sustainability, but this will depend on the ability to take advantage of the new industrial revolution and to overcome growing economic nationalism. Cooperation will be crucial; sustainable development depends on a global policy climate that remains conducive to cross-border investment”.

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